

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

M4.4 Third Living Lab for Building Simulation- Based Scenario Analyses and Policy Design

VERSION 1.0

Acknowledgment: This project is part of the PRIMA Programme supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 1923.

Disclaimer: The content of this publication is solely responsibility of the authors and it does not represent the view of the PRIMA Foundation.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8199840](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199840)

Project Information

Project Title	Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean		
Project Acronym	InTheMED	Grant Agreement Number	1923
Program	Horizon 2020		
Type of Action	Water RIA – Research and Innovation Action		
Start Date	March 1, 2020	Duration	36 months
Project Coordinator	Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), Spain		
Consortium	<p>Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), Spain</p> <p>Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung (UFZ), Germany</p> <p>Università degli Studi di Parma (UNIPR), Italy</p> <p>Boğaziçi Üniversitesi (BU), Turkey</p> <p>Centre de Recherches et des Technologies des Eaux (CERTE), Tunisie</p> <p>Technical University of Crete (TUC), Greece</p> <p>Associação do Instituto Superior Técnico para a Investigação e Desenvolvimento (IST-ID), Portugal</p>		

Document Information

Milestone Number	M4.4	Deliverable Name	Third Living Lab for Building Simulation-Based Scenario Analyses and Policy Design	
Work Package number	WP4	Work Package Title	Innovative Governance and Socio-Economic Assessment in the MED	
Due Date	Contractual (revised)	August 31, 2023	Actual	July 31, 2023
Version Number	1.0			
Deliverable Type	report (R)	Dissemination Level	public (PU)	
Authors	Ali Kerem Saysel, Irem Daloğlu Çetinkaya, Izel Uygur, Nadim Copty			
Reviewer(s)	Janire Uribe-Asarta J. Jaime Gómez-Hernández			

Document History

Version	Date	Stage	Reviewed by
0.1	25/07/2023	First draft	All
1.0	26/07/2023	First version	Janire Uribe-Asarta J. Jaime Gómez-Hernández

Table of Contents

Project Information	2
Document Information.....	3
Document History	3
Table of Contents	4
List of Figures	5
List of Tables.....	5
Executive Summary	6
1. Introduction	7
2. Third Living Lab for the Konya Closed Basin, Turkey Case Study	8
2.1. Process Towards the Workshop	8
2.2. Attendance to the Workshop	8
2.3. Workshop Program.....	10
2.4. Workshop Activities.....	11
1 st and 2 nd Sessions: Morning Breakouts	11
3 rd Session: Morning plenary	13
4 th and 5 th sessions: Afternoon breakout and plenary	15
Closing session	16
2.5. Fundamental Outcomes	18
3. The Road Ahead	20
4. References	21

List of Figures

Figure 1. Group photograph during the workshop	8
Figure 2. Cost and price table and b) the calculations template for break-out group facilitation to decide on “target crop yields”	12
Figure 3. Water consumption and cost estimates.....	12
Figure 4. Calculations and simulations at the morning breakout of farmers	13
Figure 5. Model Interface.....	14
Figure 6. A farmer presenting his breakout group’s simulation findings in the plenary	15
Figure 7. Plenary discussion on crop land targets	16

List of Tables

Table 1. Table of attendees to the third workshop of the living lab.....	9
Table 2. Workshop program.....	10

Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies, located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to establish efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

The objective of this document is to report the process conducted in the third living lab in Konya, Turkey, on March 21st, 2023. The aim of the third living lab is simulation-based scenario analysis and policy design.

1. Introduction

This is the documentation of M4.4 of the “Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean” Grant Agreement Number 1923 project.

The document provides information on the preparations, participants, and activities of the milestone M4.4 “Third Living Lab for building simulation-based scenario analyses and policy design”.

The purpose of the third living lab (M4.4) held on March 21, 2023, in Konya city center was to use the simulation model developed after the second workshop as a platform for scenario analysis and policy design and to build a shared understanding on available policy options that would alleviate sustainable use of groundwater resources.

2. Third Living Lab for the Konya Closed Basin, Turkey Case Study

2.1. Process Towards the Workshop

Between the second and third workshops (reported in Saysel et al., 2022a and in this document, respectively), the system dynamics simulation model was created (reported in Saysel et al., 2022b). Before the preparation of this document, we conducted the third fieldwork in January 2023 for model testing and trust building to prepare for the final workshop. During the fieldwork we approached six of our living-lab constituents in half day visits in three days and presented model-based scenarios and policy analysis on a simulator interface. Meetings started with a presentation on the timeline of our collaborative work and the model concept, focusing on its boundaries, purposes, and overview of its sectoral structure. We presented and discussed the relevance, plausibility and the causes of surprises observed in model simulations. Feedback before the final workshop clarified model ambiguities and our view on the workshop design.

2.2. Attendance to the Workshop

The list of attendees to the third living lab is presented below in Table 1 and Figure 1 shows a photo with the research team and the attendees during the day.

Figure 1. Group photograph during the workshop

Table 1. Table of attendees to the third workshop of the living lab

Affiliation	Title/Occupation
Konya Plains Project Regional Development Administration (KOP)	Project Development Coordinator and his team (3)
DSI	Groundwater Department Director
	Surface Water Department Director
Konya Leader Farmer Association	President
	Volunteer
	Farmers (5)
Cihanbeyli Chamber of Agriculture	Chamber division head
Universities and academia	Professors (4)
	PhD Students (2)
Turkish Foundation for Combatting Erosion (TEMA)	Officer
Çumra Irrigation Union	Officers (2)
Provincial Directorate of Agriculture and Forestry	Officers (2)
Çumra Chamber of Agriculture	Officers (2)
Ova Irrigation Union	Officer
Çumra Directorate of Agriculture	Officer
Total	28

2.3. Workshop Program

The workshop consisted of morning and afternoon sessions and the program is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Workshop program

09:00	Meeting and greeting
09:30	Opening Reviewing of the past activities. Water budget of the Konya Closed Basin Purpose of the day and the outline
10:00	<u>Morning breakout groups work:</u> Setting crop yield targets
10:40	Break
11:00	<u>Morning breakout groups work (cont.):</u> Simulating crop yield targets
11:30	<u>Morning plenary:</u> Debriefing of simulation results
12:00	Lunch
13:00	<u>Afternoon breakout groups work:</u> Setting and simulating crop choices
14:00	Break
14:20	<u>Afternoon plenary:</u> Debriefing of simulation results
14:50	Closing

2.4. Workshop Activities

Third workshop focused on model-based policy design and was conducted in Konya city center. This workshop followed the fieldwork on model validation conducted in January 2023, consisting of six visits in three days, interviewing 19 people on model structure and behavior. 28 people joined the workshop, 15 of them following the living lab since its inception in Fall 2021. The day was organized around the first two problem layers of the second workshop (Saysel et al., 2022a) exploring the impact of “irrigated crop yield targets” and “irrigated cropland targets” on key performance measures. The workshop opened with a progress presentation of the project team (20 min), emphasizing modeling and validation of both the system dynamics and the hydrological models, and continued with four breakout groups of seven people.

1st and 2nd Sessions: Morning Breakouts

Four breakout groups were designed with respect to their professional interests. Farmers, water authority, academics and agricultural authorities built four breakout groups of almost equal size. First session was 40 minutes focusing on the first problem. Co-facilitators guided the break-out participants on price and cost figures on a template for exercising on expected crop profits corresponding to crop yield targets for winter cereals, summer cereal and sugar beets (see Figure 2). Facilitators noted that “the prices and costs on the table are not exact but are very close to real figures ... Target yield would have implications on groundwater consumption ... Over the years, groundwater level can change, which also would affect the costs ...”. To observe possible water consumption corresponding to yield targets and to calculate water costs corresponding to assumed depth, the exercise was supported with graphical illustrations in Figure 3. With this information, the group iteratively worked out target yields for the three crops (winter cereals, summer cereal and sugar beets). After a break, they simulated their decision on the model, available to them through the model interface. Figure 4 illustrates the calculations and simulation activities at a breakout group.

	Crop price (TL/kg)	Yield recent years (kg/da)	Gwater consumption recent years (m3/da)	Water cost at 50 m depth (TL/m3)	Other costs (TL/da)	Profit (TL/da)
Beet	1	9000	3000	1	2200	?
Corn	6	2000	2500	1	3500	?
Cereal (irrigated)	7	700	800	1	2200	?
Cereal (rainfed)	7	350	0	1	2000	?

Crop price (TL/kg)	x	Yield recent years (kg/da)	=	Revenue (TL/da)
	x		=	
Gwater consumption recent years (m3/da)	x	Water cost at 50 m depth (TL/m3)	=	Gwater cost (TL/ da)
	x		=	
Gwater cost (TL/da)	+	Other costs (TL/da)	=	Total cost (TL/da)
	+		=	
Revenue (TL/da)	-	Total cost (TL/da)	=	Profit (TL/da)
	-		=	

Figure 2. Cost and price table and b) the calculations template for break-out group facilitation to decide on “target crop yields”

Figure 3. Water consumption and cost estimates

Figure 4. Calculations and simulations at the morning breakout of farmers

3rd Session: Morning plenary

While the feedback-rich model developed after the second workshop (Saysel et al., 2022a) documented by Saysel et al. (2022c) simulated target yields through factor adjustment and goal setting loops, the version underlying the interface in Figure 5 is a relatively simplified version of it, where the yield targets are exogenous and constant over the next 20 years. In the

third session (30 min) the breakout groups presented their observations to the plenary. The boom and decline in number of wells caused by declining water levels, corresponding shift towards rainfed agriculture were notable observations and subject of plenary debate. The behavior patterns were quite robust to different yield targets. Simulator also allowed the participants to play with the supply side measure of “surface water supply” and technology side measure of “irrigation efficiency” as agreed during the first workshop. They also tested the unpopular measures of quotas for the number of wells and the sugar beet cultivation. Quotas for the number wells, in some simulations, leading to larger basin wide (public) profits was another notable observation. A common curiosity raised during the workshop was to experiment with crop prices and electricity costs. In future work with stakeholder involvement, a larger exploratory version of the model is going to be used to answer this curiosity.

Figure 5. Model Interface

Figure 6 shows a farmer presenting his simulation-based finding in the plenary.

Figure 6. A farmer presenting his breakout group’s simulation findings in the plenary

4th and 5th sessions: Afternoon breakout and plenary

The afternoon sessions were a replica of the first three sessions, this time answering the question of “target crop land”, with an identical calculation phase followed by breakout group simulations and plenary presentations. Since the crop profit exercises were already done during the morning, the 4th session immediately started with the same breakout groups, this

time simulating their target crop lands, rather than target crop yield. This also changed the scale of the activity from farm level to basin level, because while yield targets were a farm level decision, crop land cover target was a broader planning decision. Model was a simplified version of the feedback-rich model in Saysel et al. (2022b), this time, the logit model of crop/land choice was substituted with breakout decisions. The simulator interface was identical except the “goal setting” quadrant input variables.

Figure 7 shows participants from the agricultural authority, discussing his findings during the afternoon breakout on crop land cover target.

Figure 7. Plenary discussion on crop land targets

Closing session

During the closing session, facilitators highlighted some surprises that appeared during the simulation exercises. Figure 8 depicts facilitator presentations. These can be summarized as:

- The favorite supply line solution, inter-basin surface water transfers are not significantly affecting the sustainability of the groundwater resources; neither it creates a significant economic contribution.

- If relatively open/free access to groundwater infrastructure (well drilling) continues, it is likely that the number of operating wells will start declining soon as the groundwater level declines and its extractions become costly.
- Apparently unpopular demand side policies, ex. incentives for less water demanding crops, quotas on irrigated crops, metering to reduce water consumption per land etc. are to the benefit of the region-scale agricultural economy. This is emphasizing the tragedy of the commons nature of the problem and highlighting the need for cooperation and coordination to reduce water consumption.

Figure 8. Facilitators highlighting major simulation findings and surprises

The workshop adjourned with the promise of the project team to publish the simulator on-line with sufficient instructions and guidelines to make it available to interested parties who have not been a part of the living lab since its inception.

2.5. Fundamental Outcomes

This workshop was the last, among a sequence of activities that aimed at building a living lab of stakeholders of groundwater use in Konya Closed Basin, for multi sectoral policy exploration. This final workshop fulfilled the promises of the research team to the stakeholders over the last two years, starting from the problem identification phase to conceptual models and to simulation models for live policy exploration. It helped to build long lasting learning spaces, where the outcomes of this research can further be developed and explored for sustainable use of groundwater resources.

Beyond this processual outcome of building a living lab, the model-based policy exploration pointed towards other tangible outcomes:

- Multiple stakeholder involvement and engagement in policy exploration helps eliciting multiple perspectives regarding the problems and their alleged solutions.
- The perspectives on problems and solutions can often be in conflict, which builds an impediment against viable, socially desirable, long-term outcomes in resource use.
- Active but carefully facilitated engagement of parties with conflicting goals and views in sustainability analysis can catalyze a dialogue and learning process.
- System dynamics approach embedded in community building, group model building, simulation model building and analysis is cognitively demanding. However, when sufficiently supported with other qualitative and quantitative methods, as in our example, can become more engaging and learning outcomes can increase.
- Our workshops highlighted the need for an emphasis in stock-flow thinking regarding groundwater sustainability problems.
- Our workshops also showed that separately thinking around the demand side and supply side problems are important.
- These living lab processes showed that academicians are more confused around their research interests and have difficulties in actively engaging with the policy issues.

- Water and agricultural authorities have stakes in controlling farmers' access to groundwater resources but their information on water use and farmers' incentive and behavior are imperfect.
- Farmers are aware that they are over-extracting groundwater resources and jeopardizing the sustainability of the agricultural system. However, they are equally aware that they are trapped in an open access regime.

The simulation model analysis created incentives for scrutinizing the long-term consequences of both favorite/popular solutions and less desired, sustainability-oriented solutions to groundwater use. Rather than convincing the participants, it created curiosity and concern, which needs to be carefully approached and reinforced by the research team as a learning outcome. These are emphasized at the closing sessions as a) the limitations of supply side solutions, b) the long-term adverse consequences of open access to groundwater resources, and c) long-term, public scale benefits of sustainability oriented, demand side policies.

Enhanced and widespread learning along these lines, among a wide community of stakeholders is expected to facilitate real life, sustainability-oriented policy making and water use practices.

3. The Road Ahead

After the third workshop, the water resources model component of the socio-economic model will further be validated through a cross validation exercise with the MODFLOW based hydrogeological model developed for the Konya Closed Basin. After that, based on the request and feedback from the living lab participants, its interface is going to be improved to incorporate economic messages at the Çumra district scale and aggregate messages on the dimensions of agricultural production under different water control policies.

The model interface is going to be published and a video will be created to explain its use and fundamental messages.

Living lab participants, and broader stakeholders of the Konya Closed Basin groundwater resources will further be visited with the simulator to request help from them for the dissemination of the platform for sustainability education at a public scale.

4. References

- Saysel, Ali Kerem, Daloglu Cetinkaya, Irem, Uygur, Izel, & Copty, Nadim. (2022a). InTheMED M4.2 Second Living Lab Scrutinizing and Refining the Conceptual Model (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6303541>
- Saysel, Ali Kerem, Daloglu Cetinkaya, Irem, Uygur, Izel, & Copty, Nadim. (2022b). InTheMED D4.3 Report on the Numeric Simulation Model Including Model Input Files (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7371405>
- Saysel, Ali Kerem, Daloglu Cetinkaya, Irem, Uygur, Izel, & Copty, Nadim. (2022c). InTheMED D4.2 Report on the Participatory Systems Mapping and the Conceptual Model (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6401942>